

Development of a Twisted String Based Haptic Interface: Design, Preliminary Implementation and Testing

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Abstract—In this paper a new cable-driven haptic interface able to move in the six-dimensional space is presented. Both the design and the preliminary implementation of the interface are presented in this work. In particular, a 2-D setup is considered, with the aim of performing preliminary tests on the behaviour of this novel haptic system. Results regarding the capability of the system in rendering a virtual environment and in a robot teleoperation scenario with haptic force feedback are reported.

Index Terms—Haptic Interface, Teleoperation, Twisted String Actuation, Force Feedback, Haptic Force Rendering.

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of the field of the well-known *master-slave* paradigm in bilateral robotic teleoperation [1] have brought in the last decades to the development of several haptic devices currently available on the market [2]–[4] for various teleoperation applications. The increasing need for devices capable of high performance in terms of inertia, mechanical complexity and workspace dimension has also led to several studies on different solutions based on serial and parallel mechanisms from academic laboratories [5]–[7]. In this paper, a new haptic interface based on Twisted String Actuation (TSA) is proposed. The Twisted String Actuation [8], [9] represents a very interesting solution for the implementation of very compact, lightweight and low cost linear transmission system for highly-integrated mechatronic devices, such as haptic interfaces. The paper reports the analysis of the kinematics and force distribution of the new TSA-based haptic interface. Its first-stage implementation, theoretically designed and simulated in [10], is presented and preliminarily evaluated experimentally. In particular, a planar version of this haptic interface is implemented using three TSA modules (instead of four TSA modules which are required for the full 3-D space device) and tested in order to evaluate the effectiveness and actual functioning of the system.

II. METHODS

The present work has to be intended as a first step towards the development of the complete three dimensional haptic interface visible in Fig. 1, composed by four TSA modules connected to a gimbal-based bracelet. In the following, an important intermediate 2-D implementation of the system is reported and preliminarily tested.

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Fig. 1. CAD representation of the 3-D haptic interface.

Fig. 2. The 2-D haptic interface setup.

A. 2-D Haptic Interface Setup

The system is composed by three TSA modules, secured to the main frame at the vertexes of an imaginary equilateral triangle a_0 , a_1 and a_2 as shown in Fig.2. A carriage named Haptic Interface Carriage (HIC) acts as control interface for the operator motion and is linked to the modules by means of three twisted strings connected to its anchor points c_0 , c_1 and c_2 .

B. TSA module control

The controlled length of each string $l_i = \|p_{c_i} - p_{a_i}\|$ is considered as the distance between the position of each anchor point p_{c_i} and the position of each motor-frame connection p_{a_i} . This choice allows to characterize each motor frame by a specific unit vector $\hat{v}_i = \frac{v_i}{\|v_i\|} = \frac{(p_{c_i} - p_{a_i})}{l_i}$. Therefore the feedback force produced on the HIC by the three TSA devices can be expressed in terms of the string tension vector $\tau = [\tau_0 \tau_1 \tau_2]$ and of the Jacobian matrix $(J^T)^\dagger = [\hat{v}_0 \hat{v}_1 \hat{v}_2]$, function of the same unit vectors. Given the desired force vector f^* on

Fig. 3. Behaviour during the virtual environment test.

the HIC, the tension required on each of the three modules can be obtained:

$$\tau = J^T f^* + \lambda \tau^\gamma. \quad (1)$$

In the equation above the term $\lambda \tau^\gamma$ acts as the lowest threshold required to keep each string under tension. In particular the vector τ^γ is a base of the null space of $(J^T)^\dagger$ and λ is defined by

$$\lambda = \max_{i \in \{0,1,2\}} \frac{t_i^{min} - \tau_i^*}{\tau_i^\gamma} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

where τ^{min} is a threshold and τ_i^γ and τ_i^* are the i -th component of τ^γ and of $\tau^* := J^T f^*$ respectively.

III. EXPERIMENT

A. Virtual Wall Environment Test

The first experimental evaluation performed was the implementation of the haptic perception of a virtual environment consisting in a virtual circular “wall”. Here the haptic interface just used the Jacobian matrix to provides a force that pushed back the human operator when she attempted to surpass the wall. This force was proportional to the “deformation” of the virtual wall, the latter characterized by a stiffness K_{wall} . The operator’s task was at first to test the limit of its workspace by repeating several motions along the x and y axis (see Fig. 3) and subsequently to test the definition of the wall by acting along the limit circular trajectory imposed by the haptic device itself. The behaviour of the system during this test is reported in the graphs of Fig. 3. Indeed, in the left-top graph of Fig. 3, it is possible to observe the elastic force generated by the TSA modules, opposing to the “virtual deformation” of the virtual wall, whereas in the left-bottom graph the revolutions of the output shaft of the three TSA modules are plotted.

B. Teleoperation Test with Force Feedback

A second experimental evaluation regarded the generation of the haptic feedback produced by the interaction with the environment in a real teleoperation scenario. To this purpose, the Baxter robot was used. In Fig. 4 the behaviour of the haptic system during the experiment is reported. In particular, the user was firstly asked to move the robot arm end-point along positive x axis direction. During this motion, the experimenter stopped the robot motion by applying a force (using her arm/hand as an obstacle): this is clearly visible in the left top graph of Fig. 4 when around the instant $t = 30s$ the force applied on the HIC shows an increase. Another interesting

Fig. 4. Behaviour of the haptic interface during the teleoperation test.

point concern the rotations of the TSA module’s motor, that in the same time instant are almost constant, since the user of the haptic device experienced a force that prevented her to continue displacing the HIC. Then, the same procedure was repeated along the negative x axis direction. From both experiments is clearly possible to appreciate the force feedback range capabilities of the new haptic device.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a bi-dimensional haptic interface based on the twisted string actuation paradigm has been presented. The study has to be intended as an intermediate step toward the implementation of the 3-D complete haptic interface theoretically designed and simulated in our previous work. The presented system has been considered in terms of components, kinematics and control of the mechanism. Two simple experiments were performed to test the behaviour of the device preliminarily: the force rendering of a circular virtual wall and the teleoperation of a robot while feeling the physical feedback of the interaction forces of the robot with the environment. The results have shown promising results both in terms of force capabilities and reactivity for haptic control scenarios.

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